

Electrochemical Synthesis of Nicotinic Acid from β -Picoline

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Manuscript received 18 February 1988, revised 19 May 1988, accepted 3 June 1988

Electrosynthesis of nicotinic acid from β -picoline by potentiostatic oxidation is reported. Efficiencies of different electrodes are compared by considering changes in concentration of anolyte and substrate besides temperature.

NICOTINIC acid, pp-factor and antipallagara vitamin, is generally prepared by the oxidation of either nicotine, anabasine or β -picoline, and indirectly from quinoline. The electrolytic oxidation of β -picoline and nicotine on PbO_2 anodes in dilute H_2SO_4 was first reported by Yokoyama¹. Kulka² oxidised β -picoline at a perforated Pb anode in 30% H_2SO_4 at 40–5° with a yield of about 60% at ca 0.7A cm^{-2} . Several short communications³⁻⁷ on electro-oxidation of β -picoline lacking in details have been reported. None of the above investigations reported the potentiostatic electro-oxidation but only galvanostatic approach is given.

In this paper, investigations on the potentiostatic oxidation of β -picoline in aqueous H_2SO_4 at Pb, Pb/ PbO_2 , smooth Pt and perforated Pt electrodes have been compared.

Experimental

β -Picoline was a Johnson (England) product while all other reagents were of analytical grade.

Electrodes: Electrodes, smooth Pt (2 cm \times 2 \times 0.05 cm), perforated Pt (2 cm \times 1.5 \times 0.05 cm) and PbO_2 deposited on Pb (2 cm \times 2 \times 0.2 cm) were fabricated. Different sizes of grade-1 Pb electrodes were prepared. The Pb/ PbO_2 anode was prepared by the electrochemical deposition of layer of dark brown PbO_2 on Pb (as done in an accumulator) using 60% H_2SO_4 .

Controlled potential electrolysis: A three-compartment H-shaped cell⁸ (fabricated through the courtesy of U.S.I.C., Kashmir University) was used for potentiostatic electrolysis. A solution (50 ml) of 0.5 M β -picoline in 30% H_2SO_4 served as anolyte in the working electrode compartment with 20% H_2SO_4 in the counter-electrode compartment as the catholyte. A smooth Pt electrode invariably served as the cathode. A potential of +1.6 V vs S.C.E. was set on the anode by a Wenking LB 81M potentiostat and the temperature was maintained at 25° \pm 1. The anolyte was stirred at a uniform rate of 1000 rpm by a magnetic stirrer and a steady-state current of 500 mA passed through the solution. The

steady-state current was the same for all electrodes. The interference of electromagnetic radiation was minimised by all possible modes available to record genuine potentiostatic readings. After 9 h, the electrolysis was stopped and the anolyte worked up for isolation of nicotinic acid. The theoretically calculated time based on Faraday's laws of electrolysis for the complete oxidation of β -picoline to nicotinic acid is 8.04 h.

Workup: The anolyte was neutralised with 20% NaOH solution to weakly alkaline reaction. The solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue (which is a mixture of sodium sulphate and sodium nicotinate) extracted with ten times its volume of methanol. The alcohol was evaporated to leave behind a residue of sodium nicotinate. It was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and pH of the solution adjusted to 3.4 (the isoelectric point of nicotinic acid) with concentrated HCl. Nicotinic acid precipitated out and was filtered. It was redissolved in hot water, boiled with activated charcoal and filtered hot. The filtrate was concentrated and cooled and the resulting pure nicotinic acid crystals were filtered, washed with minimum quantity of water and air-dried.

Controlled potential coulometry: In order to determine the value of n for the electrode reaction an indigenous coulometer⁹ was used. A solution (5 ml) of 0.01 M β -picoline in 30% H_2SO_4 when electrolysed at a Pt tip electrode (area \sim 0.25 cm^2) at +1.6 V vs S.C.E. for 50 min revealed 5.74 \pm 6 electron transfer by the substance, standardised against hydroxyazobenzene ($n=2$).

Identification: Identity and purity of electro-synthesised product was established by its m.p., λ_{max} , $E_{1/2}$ and the results compared with an authentic sample. Uv absorption spectrum of the aqueous solution was recorded on a Pye- Unicam SP8-100 spectrophotometer. Polarograms were recorded with a OH-105 (Hungary) universal pen-recording polarograph. A 0.6 M sodium borate solution adjusted to pH 8.7 by concentrated HCl was used as the supporting electrolyte.

Results and Discussion

Sharp melting point of the needles recrystallised from water revealed high purity of nicotinic acid; 215° (uncorrected) for B.D.H. sample, 214° electro-synthesised product (lit.¹⁰ 236.6°). The product was coloured white, non-hygroscopic and stable in air. Nitrogen analysis of triply crystallised sample by micro-Kjeldahl's method (Found: N, 11.22. Calcd.: 11.38%) is compatible with the calculated value. The uv spectra of both standard sample and electro-synthesised product showed a sharp peak at 261 nm which is almost the same as the reported¹⁰ 263 nm. The slight shift towards lower wavelength is probably due to the instrumental error.

Shikata and Tachi¹¹ reported a reduction wave at -1.6 V vs S.C.E. in 0.1 M Na₂CO₃ (pH 8.4) for nicotinic acid. Lingane and Davis¹² obtained a well-defined wave with same E_{1/2} in TMAB buffer of pH 9. Tompkins and Schmidt¹³ recommended a borate buffer of pH 8-9 for analytical purposes and reported that i_a was not linear with concentration unless the buffer concentration was at least 0.6 M. Our attempts to study nicotinic acid polarographically in various base electrolytes met with

little success. Finally, a 0.6 M borate buffer solution of pH 8.7 as recommended (*loc. cit.*) was used. A well-defined wave (Fig. 1) with E_{1/2} -1.70 V vs S.C.E. (reported, -1.66 V) was obtained. The E_{1/2} value of the electro-synthesised product (-1.70 V vs S.C.E.) reveals its identity and purity. The limiting currents were found to be diffusion-controlled as seen from the i_l vs h^{1/2} and i_l vs C plots (Fig. 1).

The coating of tetragonal PbO and α-PbO₂ (and β-PbO₂) on Pb anode in 7 N H₂SO₄ at potentials greater than 1.3 V vs Hg/Hg₂SO₄ (E_{red}⁰ = 0.615 V) was found by Pavlov and Rogachev¹⁴ by X-ray and wet analyses. Contrary to this expectation, a thorough examination of the Pb anode after our experiment at 1.6 V vs S.C.E. (E_{red}⁰ = 0.244 V) did not reveal any sign of PbO₂ layer, presumably due to insufficient potential at the anode. Hence it may be assumed that at 1.6 V vs S.C.E, the Pb anode does not act as a Pb/PbO₂ anode.

Several experiments concerned with electro-synthesis of nicotinic acid were performed, varying the temperature, electrode material and concentrations of H₂SO₄ and β-picoline. Some typical results are summarized in Table 1. The data reveals that changes in concentration of substrate and temperature do not appreciably affect the yield of nicotinic acid. The yield is maximum in 30-40% H₂SO₄ (Table 2). Smooth Pt and Pb anodes are not so efficient for β-picoline oxidation. It is evident from Fig. 2. that Pb/PbO₂ electrode is at par in its performance with the costly perforated Pt electrode with respect to material yield of nicotinic acid.

Fig. 1. Typical polarograms of nicotinic acid in 0.6 M sodium borate buffer solution of pH 8.7 at 25°; starting potential of each wave -1.4 V vs S. C. E.: (i) 0.001 M standard solution, h=50 cm, (ii) 0.001 M electro-synthesised product, h=50 cm, (iii) 0.0009 M, h=50 cm, (iv) 0.0009 M, h=50 cm, (v) 0.0007 M, h=50 cm, (vi) 0.001 M, h=45 cm, and (vii) 0.001 M, h=40 cm. Inset: (I) Plot of limiting current vs concentration, and (II) plot of limiting current vs h^{1/2}.

Fig. 2. Plot of % yield of nicotinic acid vs temp.

TABLE I—DEPENDENCE OF YIELD OF NICOTINIC ACID ON CONCENTRATION OF β-PICOLINE, TEMPERATURE AND ELECTRODE TYPE IN 30% H₂SO₄ (V=50 ml)

Potentiostatic oxidation at +1.6 V vs S.C.E.			
Concn. of β-picoline M	Electrode	Temp. ± 2°	Yield* of nicotinic acid %
0.25	Pb/PbO ₂	25	45
0.50	Pb/PbO ₂	25	45
1.0	Pb/PbO ₂	25	46
0.50	Perforated Pt	25	44
0.50	Pb	25	95
0.50	Smooth Pt	25	92
0.50	Pb/PbO ₂	20	44
0.50	Pb/PbO ₂	30	45
0.50	Pb/PbO ₂	40	46
0.50	Pb/PbO ₂	50	46

*Based on unrecovered starting material.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ANOLYTE (H_2SO_4) CONCENTRATION ON OXIDATION OF β -PICOLINE AT PERFORATED Pt-ELECTRODE AT 25°

Concn. of H_2SO_4 %	Yield of nicotinic acid %
10	40
20	45
30	47
40	47
50	46

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